

cage for adult emergence (34 d). For mating, emerged beetles were confined in another cage with healthy plants 1 wk.

Four to five mated pairs per pot were released on 30-d-old plants in the egg-laying cage (see figure) for 3-4 d. The cycle was repeated to obtain hispa beetles of about the same age.

With limited facilities, we were able to obtain 80% grub survival and rear 400-600 beetles in each hatch. Each generation took about 4 wk. Hispa

grubs required high amount of moisture for development. Egg hatching and grub survival were greatly affected if the plants were not sprinkled with water. Egg deposition and grub survival were more satisfactory on 30- to 40-d-old plants.

To determine varietal reactions, one seedling each of 15 BR varieties (BR1 to BR16, except BR13) and susceptible check TN1 were planted at random in a 60- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedbox at

10-cm spacing, with 3 seedboxes as replications. When plants were 30 d old, each seedbox was covered with a rectangular fine-mesh wire cage on a water-filled tray and infested with 3 greenhouse-reared hispa beetles per plant. Leaf damage was graded 7 d after infestation, when TN1 plants had more than 50% leaf damage.

All test varieties had high damage, indicating susceptibility to hispa beetles. □

Evaluation of rice germplasm against rice leaffolder (LF) in the greenhouse

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We developed a method to identify *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) resistance donors in the greenhouse. The test is based on scraping of leaf chlorophyll by larvae.

One 5th-instar larva was caged on each 45-d-old plant (5 plants/ test variety) for 48 h. Leaf area damage was measured by placing the leaf on mm² graph paper on a light table and

Rice varieties registering low leaf area damage from rice LF *C. medinalis* in the greenhouse. Hyderabad, India.

Variety	Damaged leaf area (mm ²)
Choorapundy	71.0
Gorsa	94.6
Ptb 33	113.8
Ptb 19	118.3
T10	125.0
ARC10660	129.4
Kula Peruvela	148.2
Balam	151.2
Chempan	151.2
ET5742	167.4
W1263	167.5
Chemban	170.4
Co 29	172.0
Darukasail	181.8
ARC7064	187.0
MO I	189.6
T1406	191.8
Ptb 12 (resistant check)	161.3
TN1 (susceptible check)	326.0

counting the squares visible through the translucent damaged area. Damaged area averaged 326 mm² for susceptible check TN1 and 161.3 mm² for resistant check Ptb 12.

We evaluated more than 100 rice lines using this method. The lowest leaf

damage was 71 mm² in Choorapundy, the highest was 403 mm² in Company Chittari. The table lists rice varieties with less than 200 mm² damage. They can be rated as resistant to moderately resistant. □

Adverse temperature tolerance

Screening for cold tolerance in Burundi

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Rice has been cultivated for many centuries by Baswahili populations along Lake Tanganyika, in swampy areas (780 m) or in upland areas from lake level to 1,300 m. The typical upland rices are called Pandabilima (that which escapes toward the mountain) in Swahili.

Sterility induced by low temperatures in Burundi.

Variety	Origin	Sterility (%)
B2978b-Sr2-6-2-2	Indonesia	37.4
B2980b-Sr2-6-2-3-2	Indonesia	45.1
B2982b-Sr62-3-1-4	Indonesia	63.9
B2983b-Sr85-3-2-4	Indonesia	65.2
Barkat (K78-13)	Bangladesh	32.3
Br51-315-2B-39-1-1	Bangladesh	97.2
Br220-1-1	Bangladesh	95.1

Table continued

Variety	Origin	Sterility (%)
Br319-1	Bangladesh	100
Chan Wang Ku (1539)	China	88.7
IR2061-522-6-9	IRRI	83.4
IR5716-18-1	IRRI	75.2
IR7167-33-2-3-3-1	IRRI	78.1
IR9202-6-1-1	IRRI	72.1
IR9202-33-4-2-1	IRRI	70.9
IR13155-60-3-1-2-1	IRRI	80.6
IR15579-85-2-3	IRRI	92.7
IR15579-135-3	IRRI	69.3
IR15889-32-1	IRRI	67.7
IR18476-55-2	IRRI	67.5
IR22723-RR-4-2	IRRI	70.7
IR22623-RR-4-3	IRRI	81.6
IR24312-RR-19-3-B	IRRI	83.2
K288	India	82.6
K438	India	49.0
K443-106	India	87.0
Kaohsiung Sen Yu 252	Taiwan	87.2
NR10041-66-3-1	Nepal	70.8
RP1848-54-2-3-1	India	77.7
RP1848-109-2-1-1	India	66.2
RP1931-68-4-1-2	India	90.0
Se Lin R (4767)	Proc.	97.6
Shoa Nan Tsan	Proc.	79.7
Stejarree 45	USSR	32.2
Swat I	Pakistan	74.7
YR1641-GH12-5-1GH4	Korea	90.2
YR2379-47-2	Korea	93.7
Yunnan 3	China	12.9

The greater area of the swamp is between 1,400 and 2,000 m altitude. Low night temperatures (sometimes below 11 °C) affect spikelet fertility.

We have isolated a variety from China, Yunnan 3, that yields well (3.5

t/ha) in the swamps at 1,400-1,650 m. But it is a typical japonica variety, while the local land races are indica type and nonglutinous. It also has partial sterility, noncoordinated tillering, long cycle, and susceptibility to *Pseudomonas*

fuscovaginae and *Pyricularia oryzae*.

IRRI breeding lines and Yunnan 3 were screened for low temperature tolerance in the Akagoma swamp (1,510 m) Dec-Jun. Percent sterility varied widely (see table).□

Effect of low temperature on yield and some agronomic characters of rice

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We studied the effect of low temperature on 10 rice genotypes in irrigated rice, 1984 boro season. Two trials were conducted in the same plot. The first trial was seeded 31 Oct and transplanted 5 Dec 1983. The second trial was seeded 15 Nov and transplanted 20 Dec. Spacing was 25- × 15-cm in 5.4-m² plots, in a randomized complete block (RCB) design with 5 replications. Fertilizer was applied at 80-26.4-33.2-100-2.3 kg N, P, K, gypsum, and Zn/ha and normal management practices were followed.

Temperature at different crop stages, Feb-Apr 1984, BRRI, Bangladesh.

In the first trial, low temperature in Feb 1984 (see figure) coincided with panicle initiation. Low temperature resulted in significantly longer growth

duration, shorter plants and panicles, lower number of panicles/hill, higher spikelet sterility, and lower grain yield (see table).□

Effect of time of transplanting on yield and yield components in 2 irrigated transplanted rice trials. ^a BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1984 dry season.

Entry	Duration (d)		Days to flowering		Plant height (cm)		Panicles (no./hill)		Panicle length (cm)		Spikelet sterility (%)		1000-grain weight (g)		Yield (t/ha)	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
BG35-2	171	163	150	142	71	87	10	11	22.6	23.4	26	13	23	24	3.7	4.9
BG367-4	169	163	146	140	80	90	9	11	18.4	19.0	22	19	19	19	3.5	4.7
MRC603-3-3	179	170	156	146	80	87	13	14	22.0	24.0	19	21	22	24	4.4	4.0
IR13429-196-1	172	164	150	141	74	78	11	11	22.0	22.6	21	19	22	23	3.8	4.2
IR36	181	170	158	147	72	75	12	14	19.7	20.8	20	17	20	21	4.2	5.5
IR50	170	160	144	137	63	73	14	14	18.5	20.0	28	22	20	20	4.1	4.9
IR9729-67-3	168	154	140	131	71	77	10	12	19.5	22.0	27	24	22	22	3.2	4.5
IR9828-91-2-3	177	169	154	145	69	75	13	15	19.4	21.4	18	17	21	21	3.8	4.0
Taichung sen yu 285	175	167	152	143	89	97	9	9	25.0	24.6	15	14	26	26	4.4	5.5
BR1	166	156	141	134	65	79	14	13	18.4	20.1	38	25	21	21	2.7	4.0
Average	173	164	149	141	73	82	11.5	12.4	20.5	21.8	23.4	20.1	21.6	22.1	3.8	4.6
<i>t</i> -value ^b (df8)	13.2**		17.8**		6.37**		3.1 *		4.5**		2.5**		2.2 ^{ns}		5.2**	

^a 1 = 31 Oct seeding, 2 = 15 Nov seeding. ^b Significant at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels of probability.

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